

SOME CONSIDERATIONS ON THE USE OF PERSONS WITH SPECIAL KNOWLEDGE IN COLLECTING EVIDENCE

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Officials who carry out the verification process must ensure the competence of a specialist before initiating investigative actions involving them, in accordance with Article 69 of the Criminal Procedure Code. However, we can see that the procedure for this procedural action is not specified in the law.

Additionally, although officials of pre-investigation verification bodies participate in the evidence collection process in criminal procedural relations, they are not listed as those who carry out verification in Article 86 of the Criminal Procedure Code, which appears to be a controversial situation in our view. Therefore, we believe it would be appropriate to add “*officials of pre-investigation verification bodies*” to the list of persons carrying out verification specified in the first part of Article 86 of the Criminal Procedure Code.

In practice, officials conducting procedural processes who verify evidence have limited themselves to examining documents about the specialist’s education and other documents confirming their professional skills to ensure the specialist is qualified. However, for clarifying circumstances relevant to the case, a specialist must possess the necessary special knowledge, and their qualification may not be confirmed by documents — that is, they may have special knowledge without having completed any educational institution.

Only thoroughly knowledgeable and highly qualified individuals can be specialists [1, p.259]. Therefore, one of the main functions of a specialist in criminal proceedings is to assist in finding, recording, and seizing items and documents during pre-trial proceedings and court processes. In carrying out these functions, the specialist’s possession of special knowledge indicates that practitioners should not rely solely on educational documents when involving specialists in cases.

According to legal scholar R.S. Belkin, a specialist is a person with knowledge on specific issues who is involved in investigative actions by the investigator and court to assist in collecting, researching, evaluating, and applying evidence [2, p.215].

One can partially agree with R.S. Belkin's opinion on this matter. This is because, in criminal proceedings, specialists can be involved not only by investigators or courts but also by pre-investigation verification bodies, inquirers, or prosecutors.

During the research, documents from 200 criminal cases from various regions of our Republic were analyzed [3]. These included 176 ongoing preliminary investigations and 24 criminal cases suspended based on Article 364, Part 1, Clause 2 of the Criminal Procedure Code. The total number of investigative actions in the criminal cases was 2341 of which 92 (3.9%) were crime scene examinations, 1544 (65.8%) were interrogations, 171 (7.3%) were confrontations, 25 (1.0%) were verifications of testimony at the crime scene, 103 (4.3%) were identifications, 112 (4.7%) were searches, 156 (6.6%) were seizures, 118 (5%) were examinations of items and documents, and 20 (0.85%) were collections of samples for expert examination. The studied criminal cases did not include investigative actions such as physical examinations, experiments, or exhumations (*the percentage indicators are relative to the total of 2341*).

Specialists participated in investigative actions a total of 132 times, constituting 5.6% of all investigative actions (2341), where the specialist directly assisted in identifying, collecting, recording, or formalizing evidence. When analyzing this indicator by type of investigative action, specialists participated 24 times (18.1%) in crime scene examinations, once (0.7%) in verifications of testimony at the crime scene, 12 times (9%) in identifications, 71 times (53.7%) in searches, 5 times (0.3%) in seizures, 10 times (7.5%) in examinations of items and documents, and 9 times (6.8%) in collections of samples for expert examination. No participation of specialists was observed in interrogations, confrontations, physical examinations, experiments, or exhumations (*percentage indicators for specialists' participation in investigative actions are relative to the total of 132*).

When analyzing cases where specialists' assistance in identifying, collecting, recording, or formalizing evidence resulted in significant and valid evidence being added to the case [4], such instances occurred 84 times, constituting 3.5% of all investigative actions (2341). Specifically, by investigative action, this included 24 instances (28.5%) in crime scene examinations, 1 instance (1.1%) in verification of testimony at the crime scene, 12 instances (14.2%) in identifications, 23 instances (27.3%) in searches, 5 instances (5.9%) in seizures, 10 instances (11.9%) in examinations of items and documents, and 9 instances (10.7%) in collections of samples for expert examination. No participation of

specialists was observed in interrogations, confrontations, physical examinations, experiments, or exhumations in the studied criminal cases (*percentage indicators for specialists' participation in investigative actions are relative to the total of 84*).

In performing this function, the specialist's actions consist of finding and securing evidence, as specified in Part 1 of Article 69 of the Criminal Procedure Code.

Not all documents seized with a specialist's participation later become evidence in the case. This is because some items obtained during pre-trial or trial proceedings with a specialist's participation may not be recognized as evidence later. Legal scholar D.A. Kharchenko has also emphasized this point [5, p.35].

In particular, it is advisable to invite a specialist when seizing securities [6, p.107]. In this case, it is necessary to pay attention to whether the securities being seized actually belong to this category.

Specifically, in the 200 criminal cases studied during the research, various investigative actions were conducted 2341 times, with specialists assisting in identifying, collecting, recording, or formalizing evidence in 132 instances (5.6%). However, in only 84 (63.6%) of the investigative actions involving specialists were significant and valid evidence collected and added to the case.

An integral part of a specialist's activity is the use of technical means in collecting, recording, and examining evidence during investigative actions. The Criminal Procedure Code does not provide a complete list of types of technical means that can be used in investigative actions. This is appropriate because existing technical means are constantly being improved and new types are being created in accordance with modern requirements, making it impractical to establish such a list in the law.

This means that a specialist may use any technical means and methods in accordance with the requirements established by law to identify, record, and seize traces of crime and physical evidence during investigative actions.

At the same time, the Criminal Procedure Code does not specify the types of data carriers that record the results of using technical means. Parts one and three of Article 91 of the Criminal Procedure Code indicate auxiliary methods for recording evidence, stating that in addition to drawing up a protocol to record evidence, sound recording, video recording, cinematography, photography, making casts, obtaining copies, preparing plans, schemes, and other methods of representing information can be used. The investigator, court can involve

specialists to assist in applying these methods of securing evidence. Photographs, phonograms, video recordings, cinematography, casts, copies, plans, schemes, and others reflecting the course and results of the investigative or judicial action are attached to the protocol. Although it is indicated that other methods of representing information can be used in recording evidence in accordance with the requirements of the Criminal Procedure Code, they are not specified, including photographic negatives and photographs, films, slides, interrogation phonograms, videocassettes, computer data carriers, and others obtained during the investigative action. The list of information media is also incomplete. These may include digital equipment and digital information sources used in computer technologies.

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